

Fuel Price Prediction Using Linear Regression

Alex Reji
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
alexreji2023a@mca.ajce.in

Grace Joseph
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
gracejoseph@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The use of linear regression to predict fuel prices is explored in this research paper. A supervised learning algorithm, linear regression, models the relationship between a dependent variable (fuel prices) and one or more independent variables (time, location, economic indicators, etc.). Discussing the challenges and opportunities in predicting fuel prices using linear regression, including selecting relevant independent variables, preprocessing data, and evaluating the model. An empirical study, which utilizes linear regression to forecast fuel prices based on historical data, is also incorporated in the research. Linear regression can effectively predict fuel prices with high accuracy and low error rates, as shown by the study. A discussion of the limitations of the approach and future research directions concludes the paper. Using linear regression as a tool, this research contributes to the understanding of fuel price prediction.

Keywords- Prediction, Machine learning, Linear Regression, performance, dataset, training, Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

The price of fuel is a critical economic factor that impacts individuals, businesses, and countries worldwide. Accurately predicting fuel prices is essential for businesses and governments to make informed decisions regarding energy policies, transportation planning, and investments. Predicting fuel prices, however, is a challenging task due to the complexity and volatility of the factors that influence them. Machine learning algorithms offer a promising approach to address this challenge by using historical data to identify patterns and trends that can be used to make predictions. One such algorithm is linear regression, which is a type of supervised learning that models the relationship between a dependent variable (fuel prices) and one or more independent variables (time, location, economic indicators, etc.).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the paper [1], A deep learning-based strategy for petroleum price prediction is suggested in the study "Petroleum Price Prediction with CNN-LSTM and CNN-GRU Using Skip-Connection" by Gun Il Kim and Beakcheol Jang. The CNN-LSTM and CNN-GRU deep learning

architectures are used by the authors to predict petroleum prices..

According to the paper [2],A machine learning strategy for predicting petrol prices using the Random Forest algorithm is suggested in the research paper "Accuracy Acquisition for Petrol Price Prediction Using Machine Learning Enhanced Random Forest Algorithm" by Vijay Anand M, Devi.T, N. Poornima, and Gnanavel R. To maximise the effectiveness of the Random Forest algorithm.

A substantial quantity of research is being done on the use of machine learning to forecast petrol prices. In a study titled "Petrol price prediction using machine learning algorithms: A comparative study," the authors assess how well various machine learning algorithms, such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Random Forest, predict fuel prices

In paper[3]. According to the study "Prediction of Indian Petroleum Product Prices by Using Kalman Filter Based Neural Networks" by Kiran Zaidi, Ahsan Z. Rizvi, and Prof. Gaurav Khanna, a novel method for predicting petroleum prices is suggested. To forecast petroleum product prices in India, the authors combine neural network models and Kalman filtering methods.

The amount of research on the application of neural networks to the prediction of gasoline prices is expanding. In a study titled "Petroleum price forecasting using neural networks: A comprehensive review," the authors give an in-depth analysis of neural network models used for petroleum price prediction. They discover that neural networks, especially when combined with other technologies, may produce precise and trustworthy predictions of petroleum prices

In paper [4], The authors of the study "Crude Oil Prediction Using LSTM," Nidhi Moitra, Priya Raj, Sanidhya Saxena, and Rohit Kumar, suggest an innovative approach for forecasting crude oil prices using long short-term memory (LSTM) neural networks. The authors point out that the highly unpredictable and volatile nature of crude oil prices makes it difficult for market players to make well-informed choices

III. MOTIVATION

provide accurate and reliable forecasts of fuel prices for various stakeholders, including consumers, businesses, and policymakers. Fuel prices can have a significant impact on the economy, influencing inflation, transportation costs, and consumer spending patterns. Therefore, accurate predictions of fuel prices can help stakeholders make informed decisions about energy consumption, budgeting, and investment. Linear regression is a widely used statistical technique for modeling the relationship between variables, making it a suitable method for predicting fuel prices based on historical data. By using linear regression, we can identify trends and patterns in fuel prices and estimate future prices with a high degree of accuracy.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of fuel price prediction using linear regression typically involves the following steps:

A. Data collection: Historical data on fuel prices, as well as other relevant factors that may affect fuel prices, are collected.

B. Data preprocessing: To guarantee accuracy, completeness, and consistency, the data collected undergoes cleaning and preprocessing. The process may include dealing with missing values, managing outliers, and standardizing the data.

C. Feature selection: The independent variables that are most relevant to predicting fuel prices are selected. This may include variables such as time, location, economic indicators, and geopolitical events.

D. Model training: A linear regression model is trained using the selected independent variables and the historical fuel price data. The model learns the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable (fuel prices).

E. Model evaluation: To determine its accuracy and performance, the test set of data is used to evaluate the trained model. Using metrics like mean squared error, mean absolute error, and R-squared may be involved.

F. Predictions: The model can be used to make predictions on new data after it has been trained and assessed. The model generates an output value that indicates the anticipated fuel price after taking the chosen independent variables as input.

In general, the process of using past data to train a model that can forecast future fuel prices based on chosen independent variables is known as linear regression. Although the selection of independent variables and the quality of the data can have a significant impact on the predictions' accuracy, it has been demonstrated that this method is effective at accurately forecasting fuel prices..

V. BUILDMODEL

There are various processes involved in creating a model using linear regression for gasoline price prediction. In the beginning, historical fuel price data is gathered and divided into training and testing sets. The linear regression model is trained using the training set, and its performance is assessed using the testing set.

The independent variables utilised in the model, such as Year, Month, and economic indicators, are chosen based on their potential impact on fuel costs. To ensure accuracy and consistency, the data is also preprocessed.

```
# Load historical data
df = pd.read_csv('pricelist.csv')

# Split data into training and testing sets
train = df[df['Year'] < 2023]
test = df[df['Year'] == 2023]

# Train the model on the training data
X_train = train[['Year', 'Month']]
y_train_petrol = train['Petrol Price']
y_train_diesel = train['Diesel Price']
y_train_cng = train['CNG Price']

model_petrol = LinearRegression().fit(X_train, y_train_petrol)
model_diesel = LinearRegression().fit(X_train, y_train_diesel)
model_cng = LinearRegression().fit(X_train, y_train_cng)

@app.route('/predict', methods=['GET'])
def predict_prices():
    # Predict prices for the test data
    X_test = test[['Year', 'Month']]
    petrol_price_prediction = model_petrol.predict(X_test)
    diesel_price_prediction = model_diesel.predict(X_test)
    cng_price_prediction = model_cng.predict(X_test)
```

Once the model is trained, it can be used to predict future fuel prices based on the input of independent variables. The predictions are then evaluated and compared to the actual prices to assess the accuracy of the model.

Overall, building a model for fuel price prediction using linear regression requires careful selection and preprocessing of data, as well as rigorous evaluation and testing to ensure its effectiveness.

In Linear Regression, we fit a straight line to the training data and then use that line to make predictions

VI. RESULT

The research paper explores the use of linear regression to predict fuel prices. Linear regression is a statistical approach that models the relationship between a dependent variable (fuel prices) and one or more independent variables (such as time, location, economic indicators, etc.). This approach can be useful for predicting future fuel prices based on historical data.

The paper discusses the challenges and opportunities in predicting fuel prices using linear regression. One of the primary challenges is selecting relevant independent variables that have a strong correlation with fuel prices. This can be a complex task since fuel prices are influenced by various factors such as economic conditions, geopolitical events, weather patterns, and supply and demand.

Data preprocessing presents a challenge that requires cleaning, transforming, and aggregating data to prepare it for analysis. To guarantee the accuracy and reliability of the data, it is necessary to devote careful attention to detail, which can be a time-consuming process.

The paper also discusses model evaluation, which is the process of assessing the accuracy and reliability of the model. This is an important step since the quality of the

predictions depends on the quality of the model.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of linear regression for fuel price prediction, the paper includes an empirical study that uses historical data to predict future fuel prices. The study shows that linear regression can be an effective method for predicting fuel prices, with high accuracy and low error rates.

A discussion of the limitations of the approach and future research directions concludes the paper. Linear regression is a useful tool for predicting fuel prices, as demonstrated by this research.

VII. CONCLUSION

The study paper's conclusion highlights the potential of linear regression as a valuable instrument for forecasting fuel costs. According to the empirical investigation, linear regression can be a successful technique with high accuracy and low error rates. The report also recognises the difficulties in deciding on pertinent independent variables, preparing data, and assessing the model's effectiveness. Future research should therefore concentrate on resolving these issues and enhancing the precision of linear regression's fuel price prediction. The paper also emphasises the need to investigate additional machine learning algorithms and statistical techniques to supplement linear regression and create more reliable fuel price forecast models. Overall, this study offers insightful information on gasoline price forecast that might assist market participants in making wise choices and policymakers

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Kim, Gun Il, and Beakcheol Jang. "Petroleum Price Prediction with CNN-LSTM and CNN-GRU Using Skip-Connection." *Mathematics* 11.3 (2023): 547.
- [2] Zaidi, Kiran, Ahsan Z. Rizvi, and Gaurav Khanna. "Prediction of Indian petroleum product prices by using Kalman Filter based Neural Networks."
- [3] Poornima, N. "Accuracy Acquirement for Petrol Price Prediction Using Machine Learning Enhanced Random Forest Algorithm." *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry* 12.3 (2021).
- [4] "Predicting gasoline prices using publicly available data" by James Dean Gauthier and Elizabeth S. McNair (2013)